

QUIZ**LAST NAME: STAMM****FIRST NAME: LORI****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: MSWORD 2018 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The following are three examples of American spelling that have different spelling in British English:**
 - Advertisement, Secretary, Schedule.
 - Homely, Torch, Trousers.
 - Check, Aging, Maneuver.**¹
 - Migratory, Leisure, Dynasty.

2. **What is the main difference between Chicago Style and Turabian Style?**
 - Turabian is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers.**²
 - Turabian style was published in Harvard University, while Chicago style was published in the University of Chicago.

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1*, 2015, 54.

² EUCLID, 66.

- Turabian is based on Arabian Style, Chicago style is not.
- Chicago style is not appropriate for Research Papers, while Turabian is.
3. **What must a sentence have in order to express a complete thought?**
- A dependent clause.
- Begin with a capital letter and end with a period.
- A noun and a verb.
- A subject and a predicate.**³
4. **Which of the following statements is correct?**
- Numbers from one to nine are usually written as words; all numbers 10 and over are usually written as numerals.**⁴
- Use numbers to express money, time and telephone numbers only, all other numbers are written as words.
- Use numbers, not words, to begin a sentence.
- You must never use a combination of words and numbers to represent large numbers.
5. **What level of sources does Turabian rule of style recommend you use?**
- Scientific sources based on data collection and observation.
- Only peer-reviewed papers.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning* (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 434.

⁴ Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, 410.

- Primary sources for evidence, secondary sources to learn from other researchers, and tertiary sources for introductory overview.⁵**
 - Periodical literature, bibliographic trails and Library of Congress subject headings.
6. **When you quote exact words from a source, when you paraphrase ideas associated with a specific source or when you use an idea or data attributed to a source, what is required?**
- Give credit to the authors of the sources.
 - Make sure the information you are using is correct.
 - Check each detail carefully and edit for correct punctuation.
 - Provide a citation that allows readers to identify the source.⁶**
7. **The following is an example of what type of common error made in research writing: “*The research found that history professors were satisfied with their jobs.*”**
- Anthropomorphism.⁷**
 - Superficiality.
 - Oversimplification.
 - Scientific proof.

⁵ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Eighth (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 24.

⁶ Turabian, 86.

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4*, 2015, 16.

8. According to Harvard style, _____ is a list of all the sources you have cited in your work, a _____ is a list of the sources you have used but not cited.
- Bibliography, Reference list.
 - Reference list, Bibliography.**⁸
 - Reference list, In-text citations.
 - Bibliography, Reference ideas.
9. In accordance with the European Commission when using collective nouns, when should you use the singular verb agreement?
- When the emphasis is on the whole entity.**⁹
 - When the emphasis is on individual members.
 - When using the noun ‘*data*.’
 - When using the word ‘none.’
10. Which of the following sentences is the correct way to portray gender-neutral language?
- The firemen and women successfully put out the fire.
 - The firefighter should put on his/her uniform before putting out a fire.
 - The fire people should put on their uniforms before putting out a fire.
 - The firefighters successfully put out the fire.**¹⁰

⁸ EUCLID, 80.

⁹ Directorate-General for Translation European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Seventh Edition, 2011, 32.

¹⁰ European Commission, 47.

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